

On the parameterization of orthotropic laminates to optimize composite structures

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Variable stiffness laminates

- Piecewise or continuous stiffness variations over the part
- Significant performance improvements

Automated Fiber Placement

Quilted Stratum Process

3D printing

Multi-step optimization approach

- Step 1. Continuous optimization
(lamination parameters, polar parameters)
Output : optimal stiffness distribution, design sensitivities

- Step 2. Combinatorial optimization
(GA / hybrid methods)
Output : Stacking order and fiber orientation

Yamazaki AIAA, 1996.
Liu B, Struct Multidisc Optim, 2000.
Bloomfield, Thin-Walled Struct 2009
Ijsseelmuiden, AIAA J 2010
Liu D, AIAA J Aircr 2011
Irisarri, AIAA J 2011
Van Campen, Comp Part B, 2012
Montemurro, J Optim Theory Appl 2012
Irisarri, Comp Part B, 2019

Lamination parameters

- Finite, continuous, convex set of design variables

$$\mathbf{A} = h \left(\Gamma_0 + \Gamma_1 V_1^A + \Gamma_2 V_2^A + \Gamma_3 V_3^A + \Gamma_4 V_4^A \right)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \frac{h^2}{2} \left(\Gamma_0 + \Gamma_1 V_1^B + \Gamma_2 V_2^B + \Gamma_3 V_3^B + \Gamma_4 V_4^B \right)$$

$$\mathbf{D} = \frac{h^3}{12} \left(\Gamma_0 + \Gamma_1 V_1^D + \Gamma_2 V_2^D + \Gamma_3 V_3^D + \Gamma_4 V_4^D \right)$$

- No closed form solution for the combined feasible region in the general case
- Difficult to interpret

$$\Gamma_0 = \begin{bmatrix} U_1 & U_4 & 0 \\ U_4 & U_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & U_5 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\Gamma_1 = \begin{bmatrix} U_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -U_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\Gamma_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & U_2/2 \\ 0 & 0 & U_2/2 \\ U_2/2 & U_2/2 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\Gamma_3 = \begin{bmatrix} U_3 & -U_3 & 0 \\ -U_3 & U_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -U_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\Gamma_4 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & U_3 \\ 0 & 0 & -U_3 \\ U_3 & -U_3 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Orthotropic laminates

- 4 non-zeros lamination parameters in material symmetry axes

$$\mathbf{A} = h (\Gamma_0 + \Gamma_1 V_1^A + \Gamma_3 V_3^A)$$

$$\mathbf{D} = \frac{h^3}{12} (\Gamma_0 + \Gamma_1 V_1^D + \Gamma_3 V_3^D)$$

$$\Gamma_0 = \begin{bmatrix} U_1 & U_4 & 0 \\ U_4 & U_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & U_5 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\Gamma_1 = \begin{bmatrix} U_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -U_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

- Approximate compatibility equations

$$2(V_1^{A,D})^2 - V_3^{A,D} \leq 1$$

$$5(V_1^A - V_1^D)^2 - 2(1 + V_3^A - 2(V_1^A)^2) \leq 0$$

$$(V_3^A - 4tV_1^A + 1 + 2t^2)^3 - 4(1 + 2|t| + t^2)^2 (V_3^D - 4tV_1^D + 1 + 2t^2) \leq 0$$

$$(4tV_1^A - V_3^A + 1 + 4|t|)^3 - 4(1 + 2|t| + t^2)^2 (4tV_1^D - V_3^D + 1 + 4|t|) \leq 0$$

$$t = [-1.0, -0.8, -0.6, -0.4, -0.2, 0.0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0]$$

Miki, AIAA J 1993
Wu, AIAA J 2015

$$\Gamma_3 = \begin{bmatrix} U_3 & -U_3 & 0 \\ -U_3 & U_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -U_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

A fixed reference frame

- Step 2 optimizations usually make use of symmetrical and balanced laminates to match orthotropic stiffness distributions from Step 1
- Balance is defined with respect to a fixed reference frame
→ for unidirectional material, 0° and 90° -directions allowed only!
- What about rotations of the reference frame?

Global rotation of the laminates

- General case of uncoupled laminates

$$\begin{Bmatrix} V_1 \\ V_2 \\ V_3 \\ V_4 \end{Bmatrix}_{(x_0, y_0)}^{A, D} = \begin{Bmatrix} V_1 \cos 2\beta - V_2 \sin 2\beta \\ V_1 \sin 2\beta + V_2 \cos 2\beta \\ V_3 \cos 4\beta - V_4 \sin 4\beta \\ V_3 \sin 4\beta + V_4 \cos 4\beta \end{Bmatrix}_{(x_1, y_1)}^{A, D}$$

Hammer, Int J Solids Structures, 1997

- Orthotropic laminates

$$\begin{Bmatrix} V_1 \\ V_2 \\ V_3 \\ V_4 \end{Bmatrix}_{(x_0, y_0)}^{A, D} = \begin{Bmatrix} V_1 \cos 2\beta \\ V_1 \sin 2\beta \\ V_3 \cos 4\beta \\ V_3 \sin 4\beta \end{Bmatrix}_{(x_1, y_1)}^{A, D}$$

4 non-zeros lamination parameters in material symmetry axes
+ 1 orientation angle with respect to the reference frame

Open hole plate under unbalanced biaxial tension

- Optimizations performed within Altair Optistruct, using SQP
- Carbon / epoxy UD ply
- 1088 CQUAD4 elements
- Compliance minimization (membrane only)

Orthotropic laminates with respect a fixed reference frame

- Design variables : V_1^A and V_3^A
- Fixed parameter : $\beta = 0$

General orthotropic laminates: material orientation

- Design variables : β , V_1^A and V_3^A
(with respect to local frame)

General orthotropic laminates: lamination parameters

- Design variables : β , V_1^A and V_3^A (with respect to the local frame)

General orthotropic laminates: lamination parameters

- Design variables : β , V_1^A and V_3^A (with respect to the local frame)

With respect to the global frame

Single layer steered fiber design: material orientation

- Design variables : β
- Fixed parameter : $V_1^A = V_3^A = 1$
(with respect to the local frame)

Single layer steered fiber design: material orientation (1)

- Design variables : β
- Fixed parameter : $V_1^A = V_3^A = 1$
(with respect to the local frame)

Lamination parameters & polar parameters

- Polar parameters

$$C_{1111} = T_0 + 2T_1 + R_0 \cos 4\Phi_1 + 4R_1 \cos 2\Phi_1$$

$$C_{1122} = -T_0 + 2T_1 - R_0 \cos 4\Phi_1$$

$$C_{1112} = R_0 \sin 4\Phi_1 + 2R_1 \sin 2\Phi_1$$

$$C_{2222} = T_0 + 2T_1 + R_0 \cos 4\Phi_1 - 4R_1 \cos 2\Phi_1$$

$$C_{2212} = -R_0 \sin 4\Phi_1 + 2R_1 \sin 2\Phi_1$$

$$C_{1212} = T_0 - R_0 \cos \Phi_1$$

- Change of frame: $\Phi_1 \rightarrow \Phi_1 - \beta$

- Relation with lamination parameters (orthotropic membrane - base ply with material properties R_0^{bp} and R_1^{bp})

Verchery 1982
 Vannucci, Meccanica, 2005
 Vincenti, J Elas, 2011

$$R_0 = R_0^{bp} V_3^A$$

$$R_1 = R_1^{bp} V_1^A$$

Single layer steered fiber design: material orientation (2)

- Alternate direction algorithm

Ranaivomiarana, MEMOCS, 2018
Ranaivomiarana, Cont. Mech Thermodyn, 2019

- Design variables : β

Open hole plate: summary of the results

Test case	QI	New designs			
		Classical orthotropic laminate	General orthotropic laminate	Steered fiber (1)	Steered fiber (2)
C/C_0	1.000	0.807	0.791	0.809	0.809
β	$\beta = 0$	$\beta = 0$	$\beta = 0$		
V_1^A	$V_1^A = 0$		$V_1^A = 1$	$V_1^A = 1$	
V_3^A	$V_3^A = 0$		$V_3^A = 1$	$V_3^A = 1$	

A multimodal problem

- Optimal values of stiffness polar parameters and compliance W for a given stress tensor with polar parameters R and T

$X = \frac{R}{ T }$	0	$\sqrt{\frac{T_0}{2T_1}}$	$\sqrt{\frac{T_0}{T_1}}$	$+\infty$
Φ_1^{opt}	Dir{Max(σ_I , σ_{II})}			
K	0 or 1		0	
R_0^{opt}	$K = 0 : 0 \leq R_0^{opt} < T_0$ $K = 1 : 0 \leq R_0^{opt} < T_0 - 2T_1X^2$		$2T_1X^2 - T_0 < R_0^{opt} < T_0$	T_0^-
R_1^{opt}	T_1X		$\frac{T_0^-}{X}$	
W_c^{opt}	$\frac{T^2}{4T_1}$		$\frac{R^2}{4T_0^-}$	

Julien, PhD thesis, 2010

Concluding remarks

- An original parameterization for orthotropic laminates: β , V_1^A and V_3^A
- Allows to find (more?) performant & new steered fiber designs
 - alternative designs for fiber steering
 - stiffening of isotropic parts using endless fiber 3D printing
- Optimizations can be difficult to perform: multimodality, numerical issues
- Optimization methods:
 - lamination parameters, gradient base optimizer
 - polar parameters, optimality criteria method